

A Study on Educational Profile of Horticulture Farmers of Ananthapuramu District of Andhrapradesh

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Abstract: Agriculture is a major source of income for rural people in India. The living conditions of rural people are predominantly affected by the performance of the agriculture and its changes. Indian farming is not profitable. With the advent of Horticulture equipped with modern technology and innovative practices Indian agriculture has been revitalized and the sector is reinitiated in profitable path. Horticulture is enriching its glory day by day with modern technology. The district of Ananthapuramu of Andhra Pradesh is one of the leading contributors in the area of cultivation and production of Horticulture in Andhra Pradesh. Horticulture influences the socio economic conditions of the rural people and it influenced by them particularly educational standards of the farmers of horticulture who practice it. Education raises agricultural productivity, Improvement in farmer's skills, enhancement of farmer's ability to obtain, understand and utilize, new input, and improvement in overall managerial ability. But the educational Senario of study area is not favourable to the horticulture development as lower rate of literacy in horticulture farmers. It is only 52.46%. Hence, there is need to strengthen the educational standards as it is key factor for overall development of study area.

IndexTerms - Horticulture, Education, Agriculture, farmers, production, productivity.

1. Introduction:

The Census 2011 shows that 68.84 per cent of population is still living in rural India. Agriculture is a major source of income for rural people. The living conditions of rural people are predominantly affected by the performance of the agriculture and its changes. Hence agriculture plays an important role particularly in rural India where most of the people live in. Though agriculture plays a decisive role in Indians' lives and is the back bone of Indian economy, the glory of agriculture is deteriorating as its share to GDP is decreasing gradually. At 2004-05 prices, its share to GDP in 1950-51 was 41.83 per cent; in 2011-12 it was 12.26 per cent, the share was decreased from 11.87 to 11.86 per cent in 2012-13 and 2013-14 respectively. It may be a characteristic feature in the evolution of Economic Development. But, seriously considerable issue is in the Indian agriculture sector is farming has become unprofitable due to predominately climatic changes, evade of monsoons, flagging of ground water table, that provokes farmers to commit suicide. The scenario of farmers' suicides is a quite evident for how far Indian farming is profitable. With the advent of Horticulture equipped with modern technology and innovative practices Indian agriculture has been revitalized and the sector is reinitiated in profitable path. Horticulture is enriching its glory day by day with modern technology.

The area and production of horticulture in India is increasing. The area under horticulture increased from 18315 hundred hectors to 23416 and the production of horticulture crops increased from 182377 hundred tonnes to 283391 during the year 2005-06 to 2014-15. The same trending has recorded in Andhra Pradesh, which is one of the leading state in the area of cultivation and production of Horticulture. The area under horticulture in this state increased from 1449.540 hundred hectors to 1474.578 and the production of horticulture crops increased from 16900.123 hundred tonnes to 18822.206 during the year 2014-15 to 2015-16. In the same way the district of Ananthapuramu of Andhra Pradesh is one of the leading contributors in the area of cultivation and production of Horticulture in Andhra Pradesh. The area under horticulture in the district increased from 439.71 hundred hectors to 1710.28 and the production of horticulture crops increased from 11836.82 hundred tonnes to 34290.99 during the year 2011-12 to 2015-16. Horticulture influences the socio economic conditions of the rural people and it influenced by them particularly educational standards of the farmers of horticulture who practice it.

Impact of horticulture on Socio - Economic Change:

The Economic Survey 2004-05 aptly disclosed the fact that supports the influence of horticulture on Socio-Economic change that "the importance horticulture in improving the productivity of land, generating employment, improving economic conditions of the farmers and entrepreneurs, enhancing exports and above all, providing nutritional security to the people, is widely acknowledge".

Philip rightly stated the role of horticulture on Socio-Economic betterment. He stated that "horticulture activities which are prime importance to green economy, global change and for better health and sustainability of the world and a way of life for employment creation and poverty alleviation of rural India".

The role of Education in horticulture development:

Horticulture influences the socio economic conditions of the rural people and it influenced by them particularly educational standards of the farmers of horticulture who practice it. The productive value of education has two main effects on agriculture "worker effect" and "allocative effect" (Welch, 1970). Worker effects are described as the situation whereby an educated farmer, given the same number of input can produce a greater output that is a better use of current resources. It is seen as increased output per unit change in education holding all other factors constant. With allocative effect, a worker is able to acquire information about cost and characteristics of inputs and interpret the information to make decisions that will enhance output. Education raises agricultural productivity: Improvement in farmer's skills, enhancement of farmer's ability to obtain, understand and utilize, new input, and improvement in overall managerial ability.

Prof. Tukkhraman, M. Disclosed the impact of education on human life and society. He emphasised that “Education affects not only the being educated but also the whole community by starting from his/ her family. In other words, raising sufficient number of efficient people for more prosperous society is the duty of education”

2. The study area:

As per census 2011 the population in the district is 4081148. The average literacy rate is 63.57%. The present study focuses on the study of the Socio-Economic Conditions of horticulture farmers in the district of Ananthapuramu in Andhra Pradesh state. Ananthapuramu district lies between 13°-40' and 15°-15' Northern Latitude and 76°-50' and 78°-30' Eastern Longitude. The normal rainfall in the district is 552.00 mm, the least rainfall when compared with Rayalaseema and other parts of Andhra Pradesh. The soils in the district are predominately red. The geographical conditions in the district arrive that this district is one of the most backward and a drought prone area in India as it stands second in the list of worst hit areas in the country. The district may be called 'land of famines'. The scenario of the district has changed with the advent of horticulture. The production of horticulture is increasing every year in the district. In 2011-12 the total production of horticulture in the district was 11836.82 hundred Tonnes. The production of horticulture in this district went up to 28352.01 hundred Tonnes in 2014-15. The consequent year that is 2015-16, the total production of horticulture is increased from 28352.01 to 34290.99 hundred Tonnes. The total productivity of horticulture in the district is more than that of the rest of Andhra Pradesh. In 2012-13 the productivity of horticulture in Ananthapuramu was 34.92 hundred Tonnes where as in the state of Andhra Pradesh it was 12.52 hundred Tonnes. In 2014-15 the productivity though is 19.61 hundred Tonnes; it is more than that in the rest of Andhra Pradesh whose productivity is 12.21 hundred Tonnes. Hence, the production in the district is in increasing trend.

3. Review of Literature:

Many researchers conducted studies on Socio-Economic Conditions on different issues. Kaldi vinayaka conducted a study on horticulture, but the study focused on production, productivity and growth area of horticultural crops rather than socio-economic conditions of the horticulture farmers.

Krishna's who conducted a study on the area of horticulture. But he focused his attention on marketing issues only.

Para Narayana conducted a study on socio-economic conditions of agricultural labourers. The study is confined to literacy, housing conditions, income, consumption and debt of Agricultural labourers of Kurnool district.

Badarla Uma Devi conducted a study on socio-economic conditions. But, the study is limited to the problems of women particularly dowry, in the district of Chittoore.

Dr. Hemambar H.S and Mr. Yogesh conducted a study on horticultural crops. But the study referred marketing problems of papaya in Karnataka state.

Nawaz Ahmad conducted a study on horticulture. The study is confined to the study of the impact of geographical conditions on crop pattern only.

Madhu Sudhana though he conducted a study on socio-economic conditions, the samples are ground nut farmers of Anantapur district.

Subramayam conducted a study on socio-economic conditions of horticulture in Anantapur District. But, the study is limited to sweet orange only.

Some of the above mentioned reviews are confined to other than socio-economic conditions, some other studies despite belong to horticulture; they are confined to particular crop. Some other studies studied agricultural labourers. Hence, no researcher focused his attention on socio-economic conditions of horticulture farmers in Ananthapuramu district. Hence, there is a need to conduct a study and try to find out the Socio-Economic Conditions particularly educational conditions of horticulture farmers of Ananthapuramu district as it is key factor to determine the production and productivity of horticulture.

4. Objectives:

1. To study the educational levels of horticulture farmers in the research area of the district.
2. To study the educational Senario of family members of horticulture farmers in the study area.
3. To suggest proper implications to strengthen Horticulture development in Ananthapuramu district.
- 4.

5. Hypotheses:

1. There is no difference in the education levels of various respondents in study area.
2. There is no difference in enrolment of children for education and literacy level in spouses of sample respondents in the research area.

6. Methodology:

The study was conducted in Ananthapuramu district of Andhra Pradesh state of India. The present study is based on both primary and secondary data and Stratified random sampling method is adopted for the study. In the first stage entire district is divided into five revenue divisions and randomly selected one village from each revenue division. In the final stage every house in the sample village was given a number in a systematic way and every fifth house in the village is selected for sample house hold and selected a sample of 370. On the basis of the main source of income of household the entire collected sample broadly divided into two categories, 122 as horticulture and rest of the households are non-horticulture category. The pre tested interview schedule was used for collection of data and the data was analysed by using appropriate statistical methods such as percentage, mean and standard deviation, ANOVA, Chi-square and graphs or figures also are used where ever necessary for the study.

7. Results and Discussion:

The present study focuses on the socio economic conditions particularly educational conditions of horticulture farmers in the study area. The study analyzed the land holdings of sample respondents, family size, literacy of head of the family and family members for findings.

7.1 Respondents’ scenario in the research area:

The respondents of horticulture and non-horticulture with community wise in the research area are shown in the table. The total respondents in all sample villages are 370. Out of these 122 are horticulture category and rest of the households are non – horticulture.

Table No. 1.1
Category wise and community wise respondents in the sample area

Sl. No	category	Community	No. of Households	(Farmers in numbers)				
				Marginal Farmers (Up to 2.5 Acres)	Small Farmers (2.5 to 5 Acres)	Semi-Medium Farmers (5 to 10 acres)	Medium Farmers (10 to 25)	Large Farmers (Above 25)
1	Horticulture	SC	6	4	2	0	0	0
		ST	14	0	5	6	3	0
		BC	50	1	15	20	11	3
		OC	52	0	10	15	20	7
		Total	122	5	32	41	34	10
	Non Horticulture	SC	92	26	28	1	0	0
		ST	23	0	10	9	1	1
		BC	108	17	29	19	3	0
		OC	25	2	12	4	6	0
		Total	248	45	79	33	10	1
Grand Total			370	50	111	74	44	11

Source: field survey

Out of 370, land holders are 290, the rest are land less. Out of 290 majority land holders are small land holders. Their representation in the total is 38.28 per cent that is 111. It is followed by semi-medium land holders. They are 74 in number. In percentage it is 25.52. Majority of horticulture famers are belongs to semi-medium farmer’s category but in respect of non-horticulture category majority land holders are belongs to small farmers. All horticulture farmers of SC community have below 5 acres land.

7.2. The role of age of head of the family:

Age plays a crucial role in human life. Experiences grow along with the aging of human being. He gains knowledge through experience. Age stimulates productive skills, potentiality of quick decision making, production and productivity through experience. It has negative shade also on another side that is dependence or mere consumption.

Table No. 1.2
Category wise and Age wise head of the house holders in the sample area

Sl. No	Category	Community	No. Of Households	Age					Households			Mean
				20-30	30-40	40-50	50-60	Above 60	Male	Female	Total	
1	Horticulture	SC	06	0	3	2	0	1	6	0	6	50.87
		ST	14	0	1	7	2	4	14	0	14	
		BC	50	0	8	15	15	12	50	0	50	
		OC	52	2	3	13	12	22	52	0	52	
		Total	122	2	15	37	29	39	122	0	122	
2	Non Horticulture	SC	92	9	24	29	22	8	91	01	92	47.44
		ST	23	0	4	7	8	4	23	0	23	
		BC	108	5	16	32	35	20	107	01	108	
		OC	25	1	1	5	8	10	25	0	25	
		Total	248	15	45	73	73	42	246	2	248	
Grand Total			370	15	60	110	102	81	368	2	370	48.69

Source: Field survey

The table reveals that all heads of the families of horticulture are males the mean age of the head of the family in this category is 50.87. It is higher than the average age of non-horticulture and overall aggregate.

7.3. Literacy scenario of the respondents:

Literacy is a torch which shows the way that leads us to derived destination. Human Development Report 2015 opined that "human development is development of the people through building human capabilities for the people by improving their lives and by the people through active participation in the process that shapes their lives."

The following table depicts the literacy scenario of respondents in the sample area

Table No. 1.3
Literacy scenario of the Respondents in the sample area

Sl. No	Category	Community	Total Households	Illiterates			Total Literates		
				Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
1	Horticulture	SC	06 (100)*	04	00	04 (6.9)(66.67)*	02	00	02 (3.1)(33.33)*
		ST	14 (100)*	05	00	05 (8.62)(35.71)*	09	00	09 (14.06)(64.29)*
		BC	50 (100)*	31	00	31 (53.45)(62.00)*	19	00	19 (29.69)(38.00)*
		OC	52 (100)*	18	00	18 (31.03)(34.62)*	34	00	34 (53.13)(65.38)*
		Total	122 (100)*	58	00	58 (100) (47.54)*	64	00	64 (100) (52.46)*
2	Non Horticulture	SC	92 (100)*	59	01	60 (42.25)(65.22)*	32	00	32 (30.19)(34.78)*
		ST	23 (100)*	10	00	10 (7.04)(43.48)*	13	00	13 (12.26)(56.52)*
		BC	108 (100)*	69	01	70 (49.3)(64.81)*	38	00	38 (35.85)(35.19)*
		OC	25 (100)*	02	00	02 (1.41)(8.00)*	23	00	23 (21.70)(92.00)*
		Total	248 (100)*	140	02	142 (100) (57.26)*	106	00	106 (100) (42.74)*
Grand Total		370 (100)*	198	02	200 (54.05)*	170	00	170 (45.95)*	

Source: Field Survey

Note: 1. Values in the brackets are percentages to their respective Column totals

2. Values in the bracket with * mark are percentage to the row total

In percentage it is clear in the table that the heads of 58 households that represent 47.54 in the total 122 horticultural households are illiterates. The remaining 64 head of the families are literates. It occupied 52.46. This literacy rate is less than the district average. The district average is 63.57%. In non-horticulture category it is 42.74%.

7.4 Literacy scenario of the spouse in the sample area:

A spouse plays a crucial role in a family. A spouse particularly if a female is not only a mother but also a guardian of the family and the first teacher to her children too. The corner stone of the future of a country is laid down in the lap of a mother. The study reveals that out of 368 spouses (2 sample households has no spouses as diseased) households belong to different communities in the sample area 33.6 per cent of spouses in the horticulture are literates and the rest that is 66.39 per cent of are illiterates. The rate of literacy in spouses of the respondents of non-horticulture in research area is 33.74 the rest are illiterates. In both categories the rate of literacy is comparatively lower than illiterates.

7.5. Family size of the respondents in the sample area:

The size of a family is an important aspect in the country's economy. It is very influencing factor in the economy of a country. Man is not only a consumer but also demand creator, supplier of labour force and he is a labour himself, producer of goods and services, investor and so on. Therefore the study of the family size in a research work is inevitable and necessary.

Table No. 1.4
Category wise and community wise family size in the study area

Sl. No	Category	Community	No. Of Households	Family Size in Number						Average	S.D	
				2	3	4	5	6	7			Total
1	Horticulture	SC	06	00	01	03	01	01	00	26 (5.73)	4.33	0.91
		ST	14	00	06	08	00	00	00	50 (11.01)	3.57	
		BC	50	06	10	29	01	02	02	189 (41.63)	3.78	
		OC	52	02	22	21	07	00	00	189 (41.63)	3.63	
		Total	122	08	39	61	09	03	02	454 (100)(34.26)*	3.72	
2	Non Horticulture	SC	92	12	24	43	12	01	00	334 (38.35)	3.63	0.81
		ST	23	03	09	09	02	00	00	79 (9.07)	3.43	
		BC	108	10	40	52	06	00	00	378 (43.40)	3.5	
		OC	25	03	14	08	00	00	00	80 (9.18)	3.2	
		Total	248	28	87	112	20	01	00	871 (100)(65.74)*	3.51	
Grand Total			370	36	126	173	29	04	02	1325 (100)*	3.58	0.85

Source: field Survey

Category and community wise family size is shown in the table. The table depicts that the mean and S.D of horticulture is more than the mean of the grand total as well as the mean and S.D of non-horticulture. It is ascertains that the Mean's and S.D s of horticulture and non-horticulture are 3.72 and 3.51 and 0.91 and 0.81 respectively. Though the means and S.D of horticulture, non-horticulture and grand total are not coincide the average members of a family may be considered as 04 members.

7.6. The scenario of children's Education in the sample area:

Education influences economic conditions. Education brings social changes. Hence education is not only a social factor or indicator but also economic indicator and influencing factor of income. The Socio- Economic conditions of a respondent can be measured by studying the educational scenario of the children. The study clearly said that the total school age children of sample households are 327. Out of these 309 are enrolled. Therefore the aggregate percentage of enrolment is 94.5. In sex wise it is clear from the table that 206 out of 327 are male and the rest 121 are female. Out of 309 enrolled children 193 are male and the remaining 116 are female who are enrolled in a school or an educational institution. The percentage of enrolment in male children of non-horticulture is 89.84 and female it is 94.05. In aggregate it is 91.51 where as in horticulture they are 100 per cent.

7.7. Management wise Enrolment scenario in the sample area:

Management wise enrolment scenario is another way of measuring rod to understand parents' intention on their children's education and financial conditions of the respondents.

Figure No. 1.1 Management wise and category wise Enrolment in the sample area

(Values in per cent)

Source: field data

The management wise and category wise enrolment is depicted in the figure. In the figure red bars represent horticulture and blue bars represent non-horticulture. The inference that has been observed in the figure reveals that the horticulture respondents are showing more interest on their children to join them private and corporate institutions rather than Government institutions. The respondents of non-horticulture are more interested on their children to join them into private and Government institutions rather than corporate institutions.

7.8. Educational levels of respondents in the sample area:

Table No. 1.5
Category wise Educational levels of respondents in the sample area

Sl. No.	Educational level	Horticulture			Non- horticulture		
		Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
1	Illiteracy	58 (47.54)	00 (0.00)	58 (47.54)	140 (56.91)	02 (100.00)	142 (57.26)
2	up to 5th	09 (7.38) (14.06)*	00 (0.00) (0.00)*	9 (7.38) (14.06)*	17 (6.91) (16.04)*	00 (0.00) (0.00)*	17 (6.86) (16.04)*
3	6th to 10th	34 (27.87) (53.12)*	0 (0.00) (0.00)*	34 (27.87) (53.12)*	63 (25.61) (59.43)*	00 (0.00) (0.00)*	63 (25.4) (59.43)*
4	Inter to Degree	18 (14.75) (28.13)*	00 (0.00) (0.00)*	18 (14.75) (28.13)*	23 (9.35) (21.7)*	00 (0.00) (0.00)*	23 (9.27) (21.7)*
5	Degree above	03 (2.46) (4.69)	0.00 (0.00) (0.00)*	03 (2.46) (4.69)	03 (1.22) (2.83)*	00 (0.00) (0.00)*	03 (1.21) (2.83)*
Total		122 (100) 64** (100)*	00 (0.00) 00** (0.00)*	122 (100) 64** (100)*	246 (100) 106** (100)*	02 (100) 00** (0.00)*	248 (100) 106** (100)*

Source: field Survey

Note: ** indicates column, * indicates percentages to the total of literates, respondents are in number.

Category wise education levels of respondents are shown in the table no 1.5. The table summarises that the percentage of illiterates in non-horticulture is comparatively more than literates. The rate of illiteracy in non-horticulture respondents is 57.26, whereas in horticulture it is 47.54. Hence the literacy rate in the respondents who practise horticulture is more. The scenario of educational levels of the sample in the table reflects that the respondents of horticulture are comparatively better than the respondents of non-horticulture in aggregate. When it compares the educational levels of horticulture respondents to non-horticulture respondents in literates the respondents whose educational levels are up to 10th, the number of non-horticulture respondents is more than the number of horticulture. But, the horticulture respondents whose standards are 10th above are more than the non-horticulture. Hence, the educational levels of respondents of horticulture are better.

7.9 Statistical analysis of Educational levels of horticulture and non-horticulture respondents in the sample area

Hypothesis is a crucial stage in research. The analysis what did earlier in the study has to be tested to derive inference and make a conclusion of the study. ANOVA is apt for finding whether the variance in the population is significant or insignificant.

To find the variance in the different levels of education between the category of horticulture and non- horticulture farmers in the sample area namely Mukundapuram, Varli, D.Cheropalli, Krishnapuram and Sirekolam of Ananthapuramu district, ANOVA – Test is used at 5 per cent significance with the degree of freedom of variance between the categories and within the categories.

Table No. 1.6 A

ANOVA- Test for the Educational levels of different farmers in the research area

Educational levels	Horticulture famers	Non-horticulture
Illiterates	58	142
Up to 5 th Standard	9	17
6th to 10 Standard	34	63
Intermediate to Degree	18	23

Degree above	3	3
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Source: Field Survey

Table No.1.6 B

ANOVA -Table

Source of variance	SS	D. f	MS	F-ratio (Calculated value)	5% F-limit
Between Sample	1587.6	(2-1) = 1	1587.6	1.15	238.9
Within Samples	14616.84	(10-2) = 8	1827.11		

Note: SS = Sum of squares, MS = Mean squares, D. f = Degree of freedom

The calculated value of F-ratio and the table value of F-ratio at 5 per cent level of significance are shown in the ANOVA- Table. The table shows that the calculated value of F-ratio is 1.15 which is lesser than the table value of F-ratio of 238.9 at 5per cent level of significance with degree of freedom, being $v_1 = 8$ and $v_2 = 1$. The analysis supports the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the educational levels of horticulture and non-horticulture farmers in the research area of the district. It may be therefore concluded that the difference in educational levels of horticulture and non-horticulture is insignificance. And is just a matter of chance.

Findings:

1. Majority of horticulture famers are belongs to semi-medium farmer's category but in respect of non-horticulture category majority of land holders are belongs to small farmers. All horticulture farmers of SC community have below 5 acres land.
2. All heads of the families of horticulture are males and the mean age of the head of the family in this category is 50.87. It reveals that this age reflects that experience, investment capacity, production skills are needed for horticulture practices.
3. This literacy rate of horticulture farmers is less than the district average. It is only 52.46%. The average literacy rate in district is 63.57%.
4. The literacy rate in spouses of horticulture households is very low when compare to the heads of the family. It is only 33.6 per cent.
5. The average members of a family may be considered as 04 in horticulture and non-horticulture households.
6. The enrolment in children of non-horticulture in aggregate is 91.51 where as in horticulture they are 100 per cent.
7. The horticulture respondents are showing more interest on their children to join them into private and corporate institutions rather than Government institutions.
8. The educational levels of respondents of horticulture are better than the non-horticulture respondents.

Suggestions:

1. The Government should take measures to improve literacy rate in horticultural farmers as it is the important factor to overall development of family.
2. The Horticulture department should provide awareness to the horticulture farmers on modern methods and inputs to use effectively.
3. There is a need to train up the local farmers on cultivation of selective horticulture crops which crops are suitable for soil and climatic conditions of district.
4. There is a need to train up the local farmers on marketing process and markets available to sell their produce of various horticulture crops as they have lack of knowledge due to illiteracy. It will helpful them to get better marketing price.

Conclusion:

The Census 2011 witnesses that 68.84 per cent of people are still living in rural India. Agriculture is a major source of income for rural people. The living conditions of rural people are predominantly affected by the performance of the agriculture and its changes. The scenario of farmers' suicides is a quite evident for how far Indian farming is profitable. With the advent of Horticulture equipped with modern technology and innovative practices Indian agriculture has been revitalized and the sector is reinitiated in profitable path. Horticulture is enriching its glory day by day with modern technology. The area and production of horticulture in India is increasing. In the same way the district of Ananthapuramu of Andhra Pradesh is one of the leading contributors in the area of cultivation and production of Horticulture in Andhra Pradesh. Horticulture influences the socio economic conditions of the rural people and it influenced by them particularly educational standards of the farmers of horticulture who practice it. The Economic Survey 2004-05 aptly disclosed the fact that supports the influence of horticulture on Socio-Economic change. Education raises agricultural productivity: Improvement in farmer's skills, enhancement of farmer's ability to obtain, understand and utilize, new input, and improvement in overall managerial ability. The educational Senario of study area is not favourable to the horticulture development as lower rate of literacy in horticulture farmers and it lead to lower income and lower socio economic development of study area. Hence, proper measures to be implemented by the government for overall development of study area.

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